

P.Colomo 7 (P.Mich. inv. 4130b)
Sesonchosis?

Enrico Emanuele Prodi

P.Mich. inv. 4130 is a set of small, unrelated papyrus fragments purchased by David Askren and Arthur E.R. Boak from Maurice Nahman in Cairo in early 1925 and incorporated into the Michigan collection in October 1926.¹ The one identified with processing number 11281 (here labelled as *P.Mich.* inv. 4130b) is a fragment of a codex measuring 6.6 × 6.5 cm. No margins survive, and we do not seem to be very close to having complete lines. The recto (→) has undergone significant damage, to the point that the upper layer of the papyrus has come off completely in places; the verso (↓) is somewhat soiled but almost entirely legible. It is impossible to establish which side came first in the original manuscript.

The text is copied in a florid book-hand with plenty of decorative blobs and finials. Bilinearity is broken by ι, κ, and sometimes ε above the top-line, ρ below, φ both above and below; ο and ω float in mid-line. α is angular, with the left stroke almost vertical. The crossbar of ε reaches across to the next letter. μ is formed in three rounded strokes. c is tall and narrow with sharp angles at the top and bottom, but in word-final position it is shorter and rounder and its top stroke extends rightward. υ is V-shaped, with barely a stem. The mid-stroke of ω reaches all the way up. The script is very like those assigned by Eleonora Conti to the fourth and latest group within the ‘intermediate style’,² a stepping stone of sorts between the formal round hands of the first and second century and several later styles: in our case the ‘Alexandrian majuscule’ in its mixed variant (*a contrasto modulare*). Two comparable book-hands are those of *P.Turner* 4 (MP³ 155.2, assigned late II c.; accounts on the verso assigned III c.) and *P.Oxy.* XXXIV 2683 + LXIV 4405 (Nestle–Aland \mathfrak{B}^{77} , assigned late II/early III

I am grateful to the University of Michigan Papyrology Collection for permission to publish the fragment; to Monica Tsuneishi and Abigale Mumby for their generosity in sharing acquisition documents with me; to the audience at the XXX International Congress of Papyrology for their feedback, some of which is gratefully incorporated here; to Maria Paz Lopez Martinez and Ghislaine Widmer for sharing their research with me; to Emilio Bonfiglio and Vladimir Olivero for answering queries about Armenian and Ge‘ez, respectively; to Caterina Franchi for many, many conversations about Alexander and his *Romance*; and to Robert Cioffi for his thoughtful comments on a first draft of this edition. Digital photographs of the fragment can be found in the APIS database at <https://quod.lib.umich.edu/a/apis/x-11281/4130br.tif>, © University of Michigan Library Digital Collections (last accessed 30th November 2022).

¹ The relevant documents are to be found among the University of Michigan Papyrology Collection’s Acquisition Reports: H.I. Bell’s three reports, ‘Report on Papyri sent by Prof. Boak, March 1925’ (2nd May 1925, 7 pp.), ‘Preliminary report on Nahman’s papyri, 1925’ (16th July 1925, 6 pp.), and ‘Report on papyri, etc., of 1925 consignment’ (5th September 1925, 44 pp.), of which an annotated copy provides the Michigan inventory numbers; and J.G. Winter and A.R. Boak’s letter to [F.W.] Kelsey (10th March 1927, 6 pp.) detailing the later phases of the acquisition. The fragments were part of a large consignment made by Nahman – ‘all the papyri he had in stock at low valuation’ – to make up for allegedly overcharging Michigan on an earlier sale in October 1924. They were first sent to Bell at the British Museum in London for a summary appraisal and catalogue, and they only made their way to Ann Arbor late the following year, perhaps when Kelsey – the *primum movens* of Michigan papyrology – could take them with him on his way back to London (an inference I tentatively make from Pedley 2012: 368; Kelsey’s diary for this period, held at the University of Michigan’s Bentley Historical Library, is silent on the subject). The papyri of this consignment are now *P.Mich.* inv. 3993–4130. Bell’s third report, which comes closest of the three to a catalogue proper, concludes by mentioning ‘Also many fragments, Greek, Coptic, Arabic, Demotic’: these are now *P.Mich.* inv. 4089–4130, and ours is one of them. On the context of that acquisition, see Boak 1959/60, esp. 38–9; on Nahman, see Pinaud 1993, esp. 156–70, Williams 2014, Hagen and Ryholt 2016 *passim*, and Abdulfattah 2020. The origin of the fragment before it turned up in Nahman’s shop is not known.

² On the *stile intermedio* see Menci 1984, Conti 2013 (group IV described on pp. 105–6).

c.).³ If we turn to chancery hands, which clearly influenced our scribe, we are in the general vicinity of *PSI* V 446 (issued by the prefect Petronius Mamertinus under Hadrian, i.e. between 133 and 136), *P.Köln* VIII 351 (6th Mesore, 30th year of Commodus = 30th July 190), *P.Berol.* inv. 11532 (1st Tybi, 18th year of Septimius Severus = 27th December 209), and *P.Oxy.* L 3569 (Hathyr, 8th year of Probus = on or after 28th October 282). Our fragment is probably to be dated to the late second or third century, with some ‘late’ features (not least the codex format) pointing later rather than earlier in that range.

No punctuation, no diacritics. It is not possible to assess the treatment of *iota mutum*, but see ↓ 6 *n*. Hiatus occurs at least three times, twice after the article (→ 5, ↓ 2) and once after δέ (↓ 5). The second and third could, of course, be occurrences of *scriptio plena*. There is no obvious case of elision, but it is a possibility at ↓ 7, see *n*. Pre-velar [ɲ] is once represented by *v* (↓ 3), but not consistently (contrast → 7). There seems to be a case of itacism at ↓ 4 and perhaps another phonetic misspelling at → 3; something may have gone amiss in the copying at → 4, too, but it is hard to tell what (see *nn*.).

A clue about the content and nature of the fragment comes from ↓ 3 ὁ Σεσόνηχος : the legendary ruler – a conflation of the historical pharaohs Senwosret I, Senwosret III, and Sheshonq I – whose conquests had haunted the Greek imagination since at least Herodotus (2.102–10). Herodotus, Aristotle (*Met.* 1.14 / 352b, *Pol.* 7.10 / 1329b), and most other Greek and Latin sources call him Sesostriis; Diodorus Siculus (1.53–8) and the Egyptian hymnist Isidorus (*SEG* VIII 551.31) call him Sesososis, and Tacitus likewise, *Sesosis* (*Ann.* 6.28.3);⁴ Sesonchosis is the form found in Manetho (fr. 34–6 Waddell), most recensions of the *Alexander Romance*, and the so-called *Sesonchosis Romance*.⁵

This last text is known from four papyri, all excavated in Oxyrhynchus: the codex *P.Oxy.* XV 1826 (MP³ 2619, assigned late III/early IV c.) and the rolls XXVII 2466 + LXXXI 5262 (MP³ 2619.1, assigned III c.),⁶ XLVII 3319 (MP³ 2619.11, assigned III c.),⁷ and LXXXI 5263 (MP³ 2619.12, assigned II c.).⁸ Our fragment seems likely to be the fifth. If the goddess Isis was given an active role in the narrative (↓ 2), we are unlikely to be reading high-brow history; the disembodied voice of ↓ 6 – possibly conveyed in a dream – points in the same direction. Other papyri of *Sesonchosis* provide parallels for claims of divine intervention (*P.Oxy.* 1826 ↓ 11 θεῶν βοήθῳ) and of course war, which was Sesostriis / Sesonchosis’ main claim to fame (*P.Oxy.* 1826, 2466).

³ First half of the third century, according to Pasquale Orsini *ap.* LDAB 2937 / TM 61784.

⁴ Presumably, this is the form behind Justinus’ *Vezosis* (1.1.6, 2.3.8) and Orosius’ *Vesozes* (1.1.14.1–3).

⁵ Manetho, as reported by George Syncellus from Julius Africanus and Eusebius (pp. 66–7 Mosshammer) and by the Armenian translation of Eusebius (p. 67 Karst), distinguishes between Sesonchosis (Senwosret I) and Sesostriis (Senwosret III) in the XII Dynasty, and between these and another Sesonchis or Sesonchosis from the XXII Dynasty (Sheshonq I; ‘Sesonchis’ and ‘Sesonchosis’ are the forms given, respectively, by Julius Africanus and Eusebius, and the genuine one is probably the first: Ladynin 2018: 9). The Latin translators of the *AR*, Julius Valerius and Leo Archipresbyter, replicate the form *Sesonchosis*; the Armenian translation has *Sesonk’usis*, *Sesunk’usis*, *Sesonk’us* (Սեսոնքուսիս, Սեսունքուսիս, Սեսոնքուս), the Syriac *Sisigosas*, *Sisigonos*, *Sisanqos* (ܣܝܨܘܨܘܫܐ, ܣܝܨܘܨܘܫܐ, ܣܝܨܘܨܘܫܐ); in the Byzantine recension *ε* we find Σεσόγηχος. On the spelling of the name in papyri of *Sesonchosis* and in Manetho see ↓ 3 *n*.

⁶ *P.Oxy.* 2466 was published as ‘History (?)’ by Rea 1962, then identified by him as part of *Sesonchosis* (*ap.* West 1980: 11); for *P.Oxy.* 5262 as part of the same roll see Trnka-Amrhein 2016: 21–2.

⁷ Published by West 1980 as being part of the same roll as *P.Oxy.* 2466, even though she pointed out some differences in layout between the two fragments. Funghi and Messeri Savorelli 1992: 86–8 show that the hand is also different and that we must be dealing with two different rolls, see also Johnson 2004: 27–9 (scribe #A33).

⁸ For broader discussions of *Sesonchosis* see O’Sullivan 1984; Dostalova 1991: 67–74; Stephens and Winkler 1995: 246–66; Lopez Martinez 1998: 357–75 (both of which also contain a text, translation, and notes to the pre-2016 fragments); Morgan 1998: 3338–41; Billault 2010; Trnka-Amrhein 2020; Lopez Martinez 2021 and 2022a. A translation of the pre-2016 fragments (by G.N. Sandy) is also in Reardon 2019³: 951–3.

Not that *Sesonchosis* is the only conceivable attribution for our codex. The legendary pharaoh looms large in the *Alexander Romance*, where plenty of supernatural entities also roam free.⁹ Indeed, in some early recensions of the *AR* – the Greek *recensio* α (ms. A) with the Armenian translation and the Latin one by Julius Valerius, and *recensio* δ represented by the Syriac translation and the Latin one by Archipresbyter Leo – there are three episodes that resonate with one or more elements in our fragment:¹⁰

- (i) Upon founding Alexandria, Alexander discovers a temple of Serapis built by Sesonchosis, ‘king of Egypt, ruler of the world’; he prays to Serapis, and the god then visits him in a dream (cf. ↓ 6), prophesying the future greatness of the city and Alexander’s burial there (α/Val. 1.33, Arm. §90–3, Syr. 1.32).
- (ii) After his stay at the court of Queen Candace, Alexander visits a cave ‘where the gods live’ (cf. ↓ 2) and there he encounters again Sesonchosis and Serapis, before returning to his army (cf. ↓ 4) (α/Val./Leo 3.24, Arm. §247–9, Syr. 3.14).
- (iii) When Alexander has died and his body is brought to Memphis in some connection with Sesonchosis (the link varies in the various recensions), someone commands to take him to Alexandria instead (Val. 3.34, Arm. §283, Syr. 3.23). Intriguingly, in one manuscript of the Armenian translation, the order comes from a disembodied voice that is implicitly linked with Sesonchosis (cf. ↓ 6), and in another, Memphis is connected not only with Sesonchosis, but also with Hephaestus (cf. ↓ 2?)¹¹ – a connection made also, albeit differently, by Julius Valerius (*Vulcani quoque eum [sc. Alexander] appellatione salutabant*).

Yet our fragment does not match neatly any of those episodes, nor the other ones in the *AR* where Sesonchosis is spoken of. Neither does Isis (↓ 2) ever appear in the *AR* in her own right, not even in the emphatically Egyptian α recension.¹² While it is possible that Sesonchosis is only a side character in an otherwise unknown narrative, the provisional conclusion of a new fragment of *Sesonchosis* seems reasonable until new evidence or stronger arguments emerge.

There is a possible, if hypothetical, parallel with a fragmentary Demotic story about Sesostris found on an ostrakon, *O.Leipzig UB 2217*.¹³ The last surviving words in that fragment refer to the pharaoh arriving in Egypt (r. 4) and to Memphis (5). Kim Ryholt interprets it in the light of an episode narrated by both Herodotus (2.107) and Diodorus (1.57.6–8) in which Sesostris survived an assassination attempt upon his return from Egypt:

⁹ I am grateful to Yvona Trnka-Amrhein for encouraging me to think about the *AR*, especially its Armenian version. On some appearances of Sesonchosis in the *AR* and possible connections between the *AR* and *Sesonchosis*, see Jouanno 2002: 65–7, 77–8, 97–8; Trnka-Amrhein 2018.

¹⁰ For a guide to the *AR* in its several guises see Stoneman 2008. For the relevant recensions I use the following editions: Greek α, Stoneman and Gargiulo 2007–10 (Books I–II) and Kroll 1926 (complete); Armenian, Simonyan 1989 (Armenian text) and Wolohojian 1969 (English translation); Syriac, Wallis Budge 1889; Julius Valerius, Stoneman and Gargiulo 2007–10 (Books I–II) and Rosellini 2004² (complete); Leo, Pfister 1913.

¹¹ Respectively Wolohojian 1969: 158 (translating the Venetian edition of 1842, *quam non vidi*; allegedly founded on ms. Venice, San Lazzaro 424, where however this paragraph is missing, *teste* Traina 2003: 173 n. 410) and Simonyan 1989: 349–50 (from ms. Erevan, Matenadaran 5472). In other versions, the voice giving the order is ascribed to a local priest (Val., Syr.) or to the god Serapis (the Matenadaran ms. of Arm.: Simonyan 1989: 350). In the Ethiopic version the command is given by ‘Sikises, the governor, and Kestes’ (ጸ.ኪ.ስስ:መኩንን:ወቅስትስ, Wallis Budge 1896: I 204, II 350), and I wonder if this otherwise unknown pair of individuals may be the distant progeny of our ‘Sesonchosis, the ruler of the world’ (as he is called in Arm. and Syr. as well as, elsewhere, in α).

¹² The only occurrence of her name anywhere in the *AR* belongs to a topographical reference: α 1.31.1, οὗ ἔστι καὶ Ἰσιδος τῆς Νεφερῶν <ἰερὸν> πρωτόκτιστον Ἀλεξανδρείας.

¹³ Edited by Ryholt 2010, who tentatively dates it to the first century BC or AD (p. 430).

‘The text [of the ostrakon] could then perhaps have proceeded to tell how Sesostris slept in the temple at Memphis and how he was forewarned through a dream of the impending danger’.¹⁴ This reconstruction is hard to prove even with reference to the Demotic text, but it would fit intriguingly well with the ↓ side of our papyrus.¹⁵ If a relationship with the Demotic text could be confirmed, it would not only offer a potential interpretative key for the Greek one, but also strengthen the conclusion of a fragment of *Sesonchosis*.

Already before the present publication, *Sesonchosis* was the second best-attested fragmentary Greek novel, and the third best-attested Greek novel altogether by number of published papyri (after Achilles Tatius, who has seven, and Antonius Diogenes, who has five or six).¹⁶ Considering that the reference to Δακίαις in the plural in *P.Oxy.* 5263 fr. 2 col. ii.24 establishes a *terminus post quem* for the text at the division of Dacia into two (later three) provinces by Hadrian in 118, or perhaps even at their reunification as *Tres Daciae* by Marcus Aurelius in 168,¹⁷ *Sesonchosis* was enjoying a robust circulation within a few decades after its composition. Though none seemingly as successful as *Sesonchosis*, other prose narratives in Greek having an Egyptian setting and sometimes origin were widely available, and they continue to be published from papyri: *UPZ I* 81 (MP³ 2476, dream of Nectanebo), *P.Lit.Lond.* 192 (MP³ 2618, Tefnut), *P.Oxy.* XI 1381 (MP³ 2479, Imhotep) and 1382 (MP³ 2480, Sarapis and Syrion), *P.Turner* 8 (MP³ 2621.2, Tinuphis), *P.Oxy.* XLII 3011 (MP³ 2619, Amenophis), LXXXI 5264 (MP³ 2257.03, a mysterious pyramid-building queen), LXXXV 5481 (MP³ 2641.3, Isis), and most recently *P.Mich.* inv. 4912b (MP³ 2636.01, Osiris).¹⁸

The new codex fragment shares something of the outward qualities observed by Messeri in the previously known witnesses of *Sesonchosis*, ‘libri di un certo pregio’.¹⁹ It is too mutilated to confirm or refute decisively Stephens and Winkler’s less flattering account of the novel’s style, but it adds a few more instances of hiatus, and perhaps one of λ(ε)ίψα used in place of λιπών (↓ 4).²⁰ It may be the first attestation of *Sesonchosis* outside Oxyrhynchus, but it is impossible to be certain: as is generally true of papyri from the antiquities trade, its findspot is unknown, and several scraps from Oxyrhynchus ended up in antiquaries’ shops in the early 1900s.

Narratives about Sesostris / *Sesonchosis* have been identified in Demotic texts, some of which remain unpublished. Beside *O.Leipzig UB* 2217 mentioned above, there are three papyri from the ‘Tebtunis temple library’: *P.Carlsberg* 411 + *PSI* inv. D 29 recto, *P.Carlsberg* 412 + *PSI* inv. D 30 verso, and *PSI* inv. D 92 + *P.Carlsberg* 77 recto (*PSI Com9*

¹⁴ Ryholt 2010: 433–4. The episode as narrated by the Greek sources takes place in Pelousion (a more intuitive place for a pharaoh to find himself after his return from abroad), not in Memphis, but we ought not to assume complete consistency between different sources for this kind of legend-heavy material, see below.

¹⁵ I owe this parallel, which I had initially overlooked, to the kindness of Maria Paz Lopez Martinez. I further note that Diodorus frames the episode as the reason for Sesösis’ devotion to Hephaestus, and the god may have been mentioned in our codex fragment (↓ 2, see *n.*).

¹⁶ Robert Cioffi points me to a further, unpublished papyrus of Achilles Tatius: *P.Oxy.* inv. 19.2B/78B(4–7)(e), whose image graces the dustjacket of Obbink and Rutherford 2006. As its forthcoming edition notes, it belongs to the same roll as *P.Oxy.* X 1250 + LVI 3837 (MP³ 2, Johnson 2004’s scribe #B9), so the tally does not change.

¹⁷ Trnka-Amrhein 2016: 26. For details and background see Piso 1993: 30–41, 82–93.

¹⁸ *P.Mich.* inv. 4912b: Wayment 2022. I have deliberately refrained from attempting to draw a distinction between novels and other kinds of narrative texts within this list, which does not aim to be exhaustive. For general discussions of the relationships between Greek narrative and Egypt see Dostalova 1991: 67–84; Rutherford 2013 (and, more broadly, 2016); Cioffi 2024.

¹⁹ Messeri 2010: 14–15.

²⁰ Stephens and Winkler 1995: 248. On hiatus in *Sesonchosis* see Lopez Martinez 2022b: 128–9; following Reeve 1971, she points out that certain kinds of hiatus are routinely tolerated even by authors who are fussy about others.

c) 8] v, tail of a horizontal in the lower part of the writing line, compatible with α 9] , upper part of a curved stroke rising to the right, perhaps with a trace of a crossbar at mid-height (ε?)] , a rounded trace not unlike the left side of ο 10 first trace, foot of an upright with hook to the right: ε, ρ, c

‘... all ... sweetly sing(ing?) birds (?) ... breaths (?) ... and the same on ... you happen ... another ... to me ...’

↓

].τα.[].τα.[
]εγαρηιςιςσυνεφ[]ε γάρ ἡ ἴσις σινεφ[
]υσοεσονχωσιςκα . []υς ὁ Σερόνωσις κατε[
]αλιψακτοστρατευμα . []αλ(ε)ίψακ τὸ στράτευμα μ . [
]ονστεγηνωσδεεπιτ[]ον στέγην, ὡς δὲ ἐπὶ τ[
5	5
]νιαφωνηνηκουσε[]νια φωνὴν ἤκουσε[
]ειτουβαδ . ειςτην[]ειτου βαδ . εις τὴν [
]ηθειςυνεστρεψε . []ηθει σινέστρεψε . [
]λες[. .] . ο . [. .] . αυ . . []λες[. .] . ο . [. .] . αυ . . [

1] . , a trace on the baseline descending to the right, then a trace further up; a stroke rising almost vertically and terminating in a downward hook . [, an upright with a hook to the right at the bottom: ε, ρ, possibly c 2] . , end of a horizontal on the baseline 3 . . [, an upright intersecting with a horizontal at the top of the writing line, then a curved trace on the baseline: either ετ or π 4 . [, a vertical trace at mid-height 7] . , a trace in the lower part of the writing line δ . . , the surface is very soiled; there is a trace at the top of the writing line, then one near the baseline 8 . [, an upright with a bulge near the top 9] . ο . [, before ο, the end of a horizontal at the top of the writing line (γ, τ); after it, a trace at the same height] . [, vertical traces in the upper part of the writing line, which may well be part of the same letter as the foregoing; then a horizontal at the same height, from whose middle a vertical stroke extends downward (π or τ) . . [, a trace at the top of the writing line, then the lower part of a stroke descending to the right with the foot curling upward (λ?), then an upright

‘... for Isis with ... Sesonchosis ... leaving (?) the army ... chamber, but as on ... in a dream (?) he heard a voice ... go (?) to the ... he rallied ...’

→

2 πᾶσαν, πᾶσα γ-, πᾶς ἀγ- rather than παρὰ γ-. If the first, δέ is a possible continuation.
3 Perhaps κελαδο . [(Demokritos Kaltsas), if a phonetic misspelling intervened. If one keeps to the papyrus’s text and isolates καί, the remaining λαδο . [is unintelligible, and καιλαδο . [is likewise not Greek. κέλαδος and cognates, although generally rare in prose, are attested in the Imperial period, e.g. Chariton 6.2.4, Ael. *NA* 1.19, Secund. *Vita* p. 72 Perry, [Luc.] *Philopatr.* 3. Since in these last two occurrences the word refers to birdsong, I note that the traces are compatible with ὀ]ρνέων ἠδὲ κελαδοῦ[ντων. But it is not a given that the first word and the third must be in agreement.

4 π]νεύματα ? But alternatives, although individually less common, abound. καταρροφυ[is not Greek, unless one invents an unattested compound: καταρροφυής, καταρροφουῶν, or the like (which could admittedly go well with π]νεύματα – but in a different sense than that suggested by 3). καταρροφ(ο)υ[- would at least be grammatical, from καταρροφέω ‘to ingest’, but it requires either creative palaeography or scribal error, and the verb is not common outside medical writings. Articulating κατ’ ἄρροφυ[or κατὰ {ρ}ρόφυ[takes us no further.

7 I owe τυγχάγεις to Alexander Jones. The second-person verb here and the first-person pronoun in the next line indicate character speech.

8 τινος ο[or, possibly, τι (or τί) followed by a part of vocέω.

↓

1 The traces are compatible with]αυ (αὐτά, τ]αῦτα).

2 ζ and ξ are not clearly attested in this fragment, but they both end with a horizontal on the baseline which could plausibly fit the first trace. At line-end, cὺν ἐφ- ? Or Ἐφ-, Hephaestus being the usual Greek equivalent of the Egyptian god Ptah? A historic tense of a verb in cυμφ- is also possible, but one rather expects the main verb to have been the word before γάρ: imperfect if]ζε, aorist if]ξε. Isis appears to a pharaoh in a dream (cf. 5–6) in the *Dream of Nectanebo*, UPZ I 81, 12–14 (text in Koenen 1985, see also Gauger 2002 and Ryholt 2002); she is an important figure in Xenophon's *Ephesiaka* (see Griffiths 1978, Tagliabue 2017: 138–50) and, of course, in Apuleius' *Metamorphoses*. As Robert Cioffi points out to me, she also appears in connection with someone's φωνή in the *Life of Aesop*, where she grants Aesop the faculty of speech (G §5, 7).

3 The papyrus's spelling is phonetically equivalent to Cεcόγγωcιc found in *P.Oxy.* 1826 and in most literary sources outside *Sesonchosis*. *P.Oxy.* 2466 + 5262, 3319, and 5263 read Cεcόγγωcιc with geminate γ, which is also the form attested in documentary papyri as the name of several contemporary individuals (*P.Petr.* III 100, *P.Cair.Zen.* III 59491, *P.Count* 23, *SB XIV* 11307, *P.Köln* X 411, all Ptolemaic and from the Arsinoite; there is also a Cεcovōcιc in *O.Bodl.* II 2373, Thebes, I c.). Manetho, too, must have written Cεcόγγωcιc, to judge from the mss. of George Syncellus which transmit the relevant fragment (p. 66 Mosshammer: γέων γώcηc A, γεcovγόcιc B). It is not clear to me whether the variation is meaningful.

4 Itacism. λ(ε)ίψαc or κατ]αλ(ε)ίψαc 'having left / abandoned' are perhaps likelier than ἐξ]αλ(ε)ίψαc 'having annihilated'. The aorist ἔλειψα is first attested in place of ἔλιπον in the fourth century BC (Antiph. fr. 33 K.–A. *ap.* Antiatt. λ 17 Valente; against the objections by Cobet 1873: 323–4 see Willi 2010: 476) and occurs sporadically in Hellenistic and Imperial writings of a non-purist bent (LSJ⁹ *s.v.* λείπω 1; add *AR* α 2.20.12).

6 Adverbial ἐνύ]πνια 'in a dream' would fit the context, if the φωνή pertains to some sort of apparition: 'Having left / annihilated the army (he went back to) the chamber and as (he lay) on (the bed?) he heard a voice in a dream...' (cf. κατ' ἐνύπν(ι)ον in the *Dream of Nectanebo*, 10). Richard Janko suggests κατ' ἐνύ]πνια, with identical meaning. Otherwise, in much the same situation, ἀγρυπνία (with *iota mutum* omitted), 'as (he lay) sleepless he heard a voice...'. The anonymous reviewer suggests reading η not π and supplementing νομ]ηνία 'on the day of the new moon', which is entirely possible; it is intriguing that the *AR*, at least as far back as β, places Alexander's death, as well as his birth, at the new moon (Franchi 2020). Epiphanies or epiphany-like experiences are 'highly typical' of the Greek novel, 'occurring in all five extant novels and at least some of the fragments' (Cioffi 2014: 6); messages delivered in dreams are a recurrent theme in Demotic Egyptian narrative, too (Ryholt 2010: 434).

7 We must be dealing with a part of βαδίζω, but text and construction are unclear. I see four options: (i) βαδίζεic construed transitively, which is uncommon but not unheard-of (LSJ⁹ *s.v.* βαδίζω 1); (ii) βαδίζεic on its own, with the accusative depending on another verb, now lost in lacuna; (iii) βαδίζ' εἰc, a command; (iv) βαδίζεic <εἰc>, with the preposition lost to haplography. Given the likelihood that the speaker is the miraculous φωνή of 6, (iii) is tempting: supernatural entities have a habit of ordering people about. But (ii) and (iv) are no less plausible, and the scribe cannot be shown to have used elision elsewhere in the fragment, which speaks against (iii) somewhat. We must be in character speech in any case, given the second person; a short speech, because we are back to third-person past-tense narrative in the next line.

8 I cannot tell if the scribe wrote συνέτραψε or συνέτραψεγ. The verb can be used in a military sense, of causing troops to close ranks (LSJ⁹ s.v. II). Before it, I suppose the likeliest candidates are ἦθει, πλήθει, or τρήθει, but I cannot propose a compelling construction for any of them.

9 A part of ἀλή is not an impossible reading at line-end.

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